

**DEVELOPMENT OF ECONOMIC COOPERATION BETWEEN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES OF
UKRAINE AND THE PEOPLE'S REPUBLIC OF CHINA**

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Abstract

As the field of economic cooperation between Ukraine and the People's Republic of China deepens, cooperation between industrial enterprises plays an increasingly important role. However, with the influence of factors such as the international economic environment, geopolitics, and technological development, this cooperation is also full of challenges and uncertainties. Therefore, this article analyzes the problems arising from the economic cooperation process of industrial enterprises based on the various stages of the development of Sino-Ukrainian economic cooperation, and studies the current situation from the perspectives of Ukraine and China respectively. We hope to find solutions to the problem and promote exchanges and cooperation between Chinese and Ukrainian industrial enterprises to achieve sustained and healthy economic development.

Keywords: economic cooperation, industrial enterprises, healthy economic development.

Ukraine and China have a three-fold history of economic development, that have the potential for further development. With the purpose of determining the prospects and opportunities for the development of cooperation between the two countries, we should analyze the stages of the formation of economic cooperation between Ukraine and China.

The initial period of economic cooperation between Ukraine and China. On January 4, 1992, Ukraine established diplomatic relations with China. Since the establishment of diplomatic relations, the economic and trade field has been included in the priority direction of cooperation between the two sides. Senior leaders of the two countries exchanged frequent visits and signed a series of government-departmental cooperation agreements, laying a solid legal foundation for economic and trade cooperation between the two sides. In January 1992, Ukraine and China established mutual commercial representative offices. On October 31, the two countries signed an agreement on the establishment of an economic and trade cooperation mechanism, the Intergovernmental Economic and Trade Cooperation Committee. On April 4, 1994, the first meeting of the Intergovernmental Committee on Economic and Trade Cooperation was held in Kiev. In September 2010, the two leaders agreed to establish an intergovernmental cooperation committee at the level of vice prime minister. In April 2011, the first meeting of the China-Ukraine Intergovernmental Cooperation Committee was held, officially launching the mechanism of the Committee. The Committee consists of seven sub-committees and secretariats, including economy and trade, agriculture, aerospace, science and technology, culture, education and health, and meets every two years. The

Intergovernmental Cooperation Committee of the two countries held its third meeting in December 2017 [1].

In 2011, China and Ukraine established a strategic partnership, and the two sides signed agreements to implement a series of large-scale cooperation projects, which promoted a significant increase in trade volume, and the bilateral trade volume reached a maximum value of US\$11.12 billion in 2013. After the outbreak of the Ukraine crisis, many Sino-Ukrainian economic and trade cooperation projects suffered setbacks, and the bilateral trade volume fell again. In 2016, bilateral trade volume resumed growth again. In 2017, it reached \$7.639 billion, an increase of 17.7% over the previous year. Ukraine's imports from China accounted for 11.4% of Ukraine's imports, and exports to China accounted for 4.6% of Ukraine's exports. The trade volume between China and Ukraine accounts for 8.24% of Ukraine's total foreign trade. In 2017, China was Ukraine's sixth largest export market and second largest source of imports. In China's trade with countries along the "Belt and Road", China-Ukraine trade cooperation is small and unstable, which belongs to the "type to be strengthened". Since 2005, China's trade with Ukraine has been in surplus. At present, China is the second largest source of Ukraine's deficit.

Now, Ukraine and China begin the new stage in economic cooperation. As noticed Ukraine New Times Network on June 16, 2022: According to data released by the National Statistics Service of Ukraine, in the first four months of this year, Ukraine's exports of goods to China nearly doubled compared with the same period last year, reaching \$1.786 billion, and China accounted for 11.1% of Ukraine's total exports. Ukraine's imports from China fell by 5.5% to US\$2.398 billion, accounting for 14.3% of Ukraine's total imports. Ukraine's

trade deficit with China is \$612 million. China has maintained its position as Ukraine's number one trading partner. In the first four months, Ukraine's exports to Russia fell by 13.9% to \$889 million, and imports fell by 37.8% to \$1.56 billion. The proportions of Russia's imports and exports in Ukraine were 9.3% and 5.5% respectively, with imports ranking third and exports ranking second. Overall, Ukraine's trade deficit shrank

by three-quarters, to \$675 million from \$2.124 billion in the same period last year. Ukraine's total exports increased by 1.7% from the same period last year to \$16 billion, while imports decreased by 9.3% to \$16.76 billion [2] Please see the table 1.1 below for specific statistical data on economic cooperation and development between the two countries.

Table 1.1

Statistical table of economic cooperation and development between Ukraine and the People's Republic of China

Year/ Period	Bilateral Trade Volume (USD Billion)	Main Chinese Exports to Ukraine	Main Ukrainian Ex- ports to China	Key Investment & Cooperation Areas
1992	0.06	Machinery, consumer goods, textiles	Grain (wheat, barley), iron ore	Diplomatic ties established, initial trade
2000	0.52	Electronics, light industrial products	Agricultural products, steel, raw materials	Trade expands; focus on industrial goods
2010	7.68	Communication equipment, motor parts	Corn, coal, aviation technology	Strengthened cooperation in agriculture, aviation
2015	7.10	Consumer electronics, chemical products	Sunflower oil, metals, agricultural goods	Participation in the Belt and Road Initiative
2020	15.03	High-tech products, medical supplies	Grain (corn, wheat), iron and steel	Major investments in agriculture and infrastructure
2023	17.05	Renewable energy equipment, industrial goods	Corn, sunflower oil, aviation engines	Expanded trade relations, focus on green energy

Source: developed by author on the basis of WITS [3]

Ukraine is an important node of the 'Belt and Road', and Ukraine has significant comparative advantages in participating in bilateral economic and trade cooperation, such as location, market, labor costs, science and technology, and industrial and agricultural foundation. To strengthen communication, honesty and find a way to resolve investment risks, Ukraine has an innate advantage in becoming a hub for sea, land and air transportation and logistics between China and Europe.

Risks currently faced by Chinese companies in Ukraine: Geopolitical tensions between China, Russia and the West have impacted Chinese companies' operations in Ukraine. Local laws and regulations pose challenges to corporate development and investment.

Opportunities for future investment and development: Potential future growth areas for Chinese investment in Ukraine are post-conflict recovery and infrastructure reconstruction. Chinese companies will

strengthen Ukraine's role as a hub for Eurasian trade and investment. Overcome obstacles and promote strategic economic cooperation between Ukrainian and Chinese enterprises to jointly develop markets and promote economic development.

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